

Opsporen en beheersen van nieuwe risico's - Detecting and controlling of emerging risks

Executive summary

Introduction

The increasing complexity of food production chains, climate change, increased resistance of pathogens and progressive internationalisation, heighten the risk of new, unforeseen problems which could affect the safety of our food as well as animal health and plant health. This report identifies these “emerging risks”. The social and economic consequences of these risks could be immense. The NVWA’s Office for Risk Assessment and Research (*BuRO*) is responsible for identifying and anticipating risks for the Ministries of Economic Affairs and Health, Welfare and Sport. To be able to fulfil this role, BuRO needs a methodology to identify the potential hazards in the field of food safety, animal and plant health, and consumer products at an early stage.

The task

In practice, current warning systems are primarily reactive and therefore not suited for a proactive, more predictive knowledge transfer. BuRO has asked a research team, comprising Capgemini Consulting, Capgemini Application Solutions, Wageningen Research Centers Alterra and Livestock Research, to develop such a methodology, using current scientific insights, like the Emerging Risk Detection Support System (ERDSS), as developed by the Foundation Service Agricultural Research (*Stichting Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek/DLO Foundation*). The task’s focus was to investigate whether, on the basis of the ERDSS concept, an automated device, that is, a real time working prototype, can be developed to provide faster insight into emerging risks.

Specific areas of attention for the study were: the information architecture, determining relevant sources of information, analysing large data streams and the functional linking of data streams, the integration of expert opinion, the use of rule engines and the application of knowledge rules and the indication of priority or posteriority of production chains. The research report’s subtitle is: “The user behind the buttons”. This expresses BuRO’s wish to have an automated system which will enable their own experts to detect potential risks themselves.

The pork production chain as study case

The pork production chain has been used as demarcation for demonstration in a real-time working prototype and for evaluation of systematics. Relevant risks and actors in the pork production chain have been described based on interviews and meetings with experts from the NVWA, GD, RIVM, Capgemini and Wageningen-UR. The focus was placed on actors in the chain and product streams (feed, farms, transport, slaughterhouses, processors, retail and consumers). The chain description includes medicines, possible transmitters of infection, manure and carcass disposal as well. This also applies to supplements during meat processing, as activities in this link of the chain pose potential risks to public health.

The analysis revealed a range of potential data sources, both national and international. Two risk cases were further worked out for the benefit of the prototype to be built: African

swine fever (animal disease) and Hepatitis E (zoonosis). Specific data sources were selected for these risk cases on the basis of the outcomes of two workshops with leading Dutch experts, and risk-indicators and knowledge rules¹ were determined for use in the prototype Apollon.

The knowledge rules are applied to the following data sources:

1. identification and registration data (I&R) for transport and movement of pigs from the National Service for the Implementation of Regulations as source data owner,
2. OSIRIS, the online system for reporting human infectious diseases to the Health Care Inspectorate and the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), with RIVM as source data owner,
3. GD-VeeKijker, the database of reports of suspected and/or new defects in farm animals, with Animal Health Service as source data owner and
4. VIC, the database of reports of suspected infectious diseases in animals with the NVWA Veterinary Incident and Crisis Centre as source data owner.

New knowledge rules can be developed through expert workshops. As soon as the required data sources are retrieved the knowledge rules can be added to the prototype using the prototype's Drools Expert software.

Apollon: the prototype

The automated system for detecting risks was delivered in the form of a prototype: Apollon. The prototype can be operated by the BuRO experts or by other NVWA employees.

Composition

The Apollon prototype includes three interconnected core components:

1. Software. Functional modules for analysing data, for data storage and management, for the development and maintenance of knowledge rules, for the visualisation of results and for the user's dashboard. Software packages Palantir, Jboss Drools Expert 5.1 and Jboss Drools Guvnor 5.1. were used for the modules.
2. Data. Currently the prototype contains several data files on the pork production chain.
3. Knowledge. Currently, the prototype contains a series of concepts and knowledge rules that are relevant for detecting African swine fever and the Hepatitis E.

Possible applications

The user operates the prototype via the user environment. This built-in functionality provides a desktop screen to access the various functions. It is expected that two days training will be needed before using the tool effectively. In addition, user support can be provided in a later stage to improve speed and proficiency in Apollon.² As a starting point prototype users need sufficient material knowledge per NVWA domain (chain knowledge, business intelligence and risk analysis) and basic skills in the use of current software in the area of office automation and data-analysis (data mining).

¹ Knowledge rules: formulations integrated into the Apollon prototype, laying down expert knowledge for automated analysis.

² User support for the Apollon prototype can be provided on location or via a remote help desk.

The study tested the effects of Apollon. It proved possible to identify emerging risks in the pork production chain with the aid of knowledge rules, based on expert knowledge, and the connected data sources automatically and in real life mode. To do this, the available data will be analysed electronically with the aid of knowledge rules. Certain threshold values determined by the user were integrated into the knowledge rules. When a number of threshold conditions have been exceeded, the prototype signals a possible emerging risk.

In addition to this automated forward chaining analysis, the prototype also offers backward chaining analysis (tracking and tracing for possible causes of risks or incidents that have occurred). A user can implement this analysis intuitively and in real life modus by operating the prototype manually. It is standard procedure to have the functionality for backward chaining included in the Palantir software package.

Apollon can process a wide range of data. In the prototype's current development phase this involves data from data banks of specific organisations and research documents, such as RIVM reports. In addition, users can import a range of sources into Apollon themselves. Examples are: web services, smaller database files, emails, online services, RSS Feeds and Social Media.

Furthermore, Apollon allows users to:

- connect to new data sources,
- adjust the series of concepts relevant for risk detection,
- add, amend and remove knowledge rules,
- enter and remove searches ('feeds') for data that draw the user's attention to amendments and addition of data.

Specific skills are required to be able to use the software integrated into the prototype for knowledge rules. With Drools Guvnor, existing knowledge rules can be adapted by the end user after a training course of 1 to 2 days. With Drools Expert, new and complex knowledge rules can be programmed for application in the prototype. To be able to use Drools Expert, more programming skills and additional hands-on training are required. Initially, end users will need support from programming experts to be able to add new knowledge rules to the prototype.

Added value for the NVWA

As a prototype, Apollon was set up for the pork production chain risk domain. With the properties now available in the prototype, the NVWA has at its disposal an instrument that can serve as a model to be applied to all risk domains it supervises.

The instrument enables the NVWA to:

1. **Faster risk detection.** Automated forward chaining in real life modus gives insight into emerging risks faster than before. This gives the NVWA more time to devise and implement preventative measures, so avoiding substantial social and economic damage.
2. **Faster detection of sources of infection.** The prototype also allows analysis of large amounts of data in real life modus to detect the source of infections. NVWA experts can use the instrument themselves in an intuitive way. The source of infection can be identified faster and thus reduce social and economic damage considerably.
3. **Enhanced effectiveness of own expertise.** Apollon is an instrument NVWA experts themselves can operate, making them less dependent of external experts. Whenever the use

of specialised expertise is still required, the application of Apollon will enable NVWA experts to provide external experts with more finely-tuned tasks, which will benefit both effectiveness and efficiency.

4. Improved internal and external cooperation. With Apollon, the NVWA has an instrument that in principle can be applied in all risk domains the authority is monitoring. That will improve the cooperation between the NVWA divisions. The use of Apollon also allows for improved cooperation with other organisations, for example by a joint analysis of the data of different supervising bodies and by sharing of that information. Application of Apollon enables the NVWA to get an idea of the emerging risks faster than before, whatever the location worldwide. That provides the opportunity to ask international risk experts targeted questions at any time.

Limitations of the prototype

The Apollon prototype, as it was delivered, can only be applied to the pork production chain. To do this, the prototype is equipped with the relevant knowledge rules for this chain and a number of relevant data files. The modular set-up of the prototype makes it possible to add knowledge rules and data files that are relevant to other product chains.

A second limitation relates to the retrieved data sources. Apollon's strength is determined especially by the availability, accessibility and quality of the data sources. During the study it became clear that it was not possible to gain access to all required data sources within the lead time of the project. That is why the analysis was limited to the data sources that were made available.

Recommendations

1. The Apollon prototype as it is delivered is an instrument that NVWA experts themselves can operate. This was tested by the steering committee during the execution of the task. It is recommended that Apollon is installed on the NVWA's ICT-infrastructure and implemented in a pilot to introduce experts from BuRO and other divisions to Apollon and to teach them how to use this in everyday situations. Hands-on training in operating the prototype and developing knowledge rules should be part of such a pilot.
2. The study explored the effects of the application of Apollon for the NVWA. The results are laid down in the form of a general qualitative business case. It is recommended that this qualitative business case is further worked out and quantified.
3. It is important to be able to exchange information with other risk assessing organisations, bearing in mind the speed with which animal diseases and pests can spread. It is recommended that the range of concepts stored in Apollon be further developed on the basis of an ontology that describes the domain of risk management in food chains, like AGROVOC.
4. Experience in developing the prototype has shown that gaining access to specific data files requires much effort, one of the reasons being that data source keepers show reservations in making their data available. It is recommended that a tiered working method for collecting and analysing information is applied. Such a mixed scanning starts with analysing available public information. An overall picture can then be gained of the possible emerging risks. When this shows that in certain areas there are more incidents and more fundamental analysis is required, contact can then be sought with the owners of relevant specific data

files. The outcome of the first analysis provides the NVWA with the foundation to ask these source data owners to provide access to their data.

5. Confidentiality, privacy, sensitivity and insecurity about the right use of data are important arguments for reservations on the part of source data owners. Restricted access to data or refusal can considerably hinder innovation in risk detection methodology, like the Apollon prototype. We recommended drawing up a rule of conduct, in consultation with data source owners, in which the right to access and the right of use of data are clarified.

6. The data sources that were made available for the study were in some cases not suitable to be used in Apollon's risk signalling functionalities. This means that data was lacking and that the quality of certain data was insufficient. We recommend that these conclusions are evaluated with the source data owners.

7. One area of focus in the study was the indication of priority or posteriority to production chains. The Apollon prototype as it is delivered is a system that goes beyond one production chain, providing NVWA the advantage of detecting risks in several production chains if generic data – relevant to several production chains - is incorporated. We recommend granting priority or posteriority to such generic data sources as an approach for the further development of Apollon and not to specific production chains.